

EARLY DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH DETECTIVE GENRE

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the study of detective literature, which is one of its own genres. It discusses and analyzes information and materials about the detective genre and its history, that is, how it appeared, the years of its appearance.

Key words: detective genre, protagonist, emotional matter, reality

Detective genre is a type of literary genre in which a detective or investigator investigates a professional, retired, or amateur murder. The detective genre emerged simultaneously with speculative fiction and alternative genre fiction in the mid-nineteenth century, and became an extraordinary standard, especially in novels starring the most famous heroes of detective fiction, C. Auguste Dupin, character and Hercules. Arrived at Poirot. Stories about minors, including The Hardy Boys, Nancy Drew, have been published for decades, in addition to the youth of freight cars. Some studio staff, such as R. H. Pfeiffer, said that ancient and spiritual texts had similarities to what was later called detective fiction. In Susanna and therefore in the will of the Elders (the Protestant Bible finds this event in the apocryphal range), the story told by two witnesses failed after Daniel cross-examined them. In response, as author Solon Simons points out, "The United Nations agency is looking for identifying passages within the Bible and the Herodotus Territorial Division that only want puzzles," these puzzles are not detective stories. In the play of the legendary creature of the ancient Greek writer, the legendary creature investigates the unsolved murder of the legendary creature of the king, and when he interrogates many witnesses, he finds himself guilty.

"Although Oedipus inquiry is based on the supernatural, preconceived notions that appear in many narrations about crime before the Enlightenment in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries," this narration is "has all the central features and formal parts.

Early Arab Detective Fiction: A Thousand and One Nights is one of the oldest detective stories about modern detective fiction. The most ancient famous example of the person was "3 apples" which is one of the tales narrated by Shirzad in the context of Thousand and One Nights (Arab Nights). During this story, a trained worker finds an important, bolted box in the river and sells it to Abbas Muhammad, Harun al-Rashid. When Aaron breaks his chest and opens it, he finds the body of a woman whose things have been removed. Aaron then orders his officer Ja'far ibn Yahya to solve the crime and to find the culprit within 3 days or die if he fails to complete the task. Suspicion arises through the several plot twists that occur as a result of the development of the story. With these features, this detective could be a thought-provoking associative example for fiction.

He expects to use reverse chronology in modern detective fiction, where the story is against the law, before presenting a gradual reconstruction of the past. The main difference between Jaffar and the next fantasy detectives, for example, the fantasy hero and Hercules Poirot, is that Jaffar doesn't want to solve the case. The mystery of the mysterious story is solved after the perpetrator himself confesses to the crime. This concludes with the next assignment, during which time Jaffar should have known that the perpetrator of the murder was dead

within 3 days. Jaffar couldn't look for the culprit again before he spoke, but chances are he found the main thing. Eventually, he manages to resolve the case by meditating to prevent his execution.

On the other hand, two alternative entertainment stories, "The Entrepreneur and the Thief" and "Ali Hoja," reveal the 2 oldest fictional detectives who reveal tips and gifts to catch or convict a criminal includes the audience, the story flourished in the traditional chronology and therefore the culprit is already well known to the audience. While detective protagonist Ali Hoja presents the evidence of qualified witnesses in court, the latter involves a climax. One of the earliest examples of detective fiction in Western literature is Voltaire's *Zadik* (1748), in which he chooses a protagonist who is courageous in his study. Things in their own right; or, "The Adventures of Kaleb Williams" (1794), written by William Godwin, describes the law as the protection of the offender and the extermination of the innocent.

Thomas Skinner Sturr's life stories of an anonymous state capital, or Bow Street officer, were revealed in London in 1827; The Danish crime story was written in 1829 by Steil Steensen Blicher, priest of Veilbye; Mauritz Hansen's Norwegian crime novel *Mordet paa Maskinbygger Rulfsen* ("The Murder of Engineer Rulfsen") was published in December 1839. the innocence of a favorite suspect of the police in the murder of a jeweler. This story is usually cited for his first influence on King Allan Poe's "Murders on Morgie Street" (1841). The "Secret Cell" that may have influenced the author is a short story opened in September 1837 by William Evans Burton. This story was instructed in 1839 by an author who worked for Burton to be famous. The story involves several London officers who solve the mystery of the woman they captured. Instead of the imagination or the brilliance of the mind, Burton's imaginary detective relied on clever strategies such as bulldog legs, information about the underworld, and police work. In the communicative world, detective fiction began in 1841 with Poe's "Murders on Morgie Street," which included "early August detective, eccentric, and intelligent C. Auguste Dupin. Once the initial part of the character. when it appeared, the word detective was not used in English; but the protagonist's name "Dupin" is derived from the English word dupe or deception. The author has devised a plot formula that provides or receives a number of variables.

Poe called his stories "confirmation tales. In stories like this, the first concern of the plot is to discover the truth, and achieving reality can be a complex and mysterious method that incorporates intuitive logic, intelligent observation, and intelligent reasoning. The first detective stories involved follow the protagonist from the main scene to the end, which creates a clever feeling instead of emotional matter. "The Secret of Marie Roger" is particularly noteworthy because it is a barely fictional story that supports Poe's theory of what happened to Madonna Cecilia Rogers in real life.

Literary critic Catherine Ross Nickerson is thankful for creating Louise May Alcott's second oldest work in recent detective fiction, the 1865 heroic tale "V.V. or Plots and Contradictions," which was once Po's Dupin's story. A short story revealed anonymously by Alcott, the story is told by a blue-blooded UN agency in Scotland trying to prove that a mysterious girl killed her fiancé and cousin German. Detective Antoine Dupres, in this case, may be a parody of August Dupin, the UN agency is less concerned with finding the culprit because it has put forward the simplest way to uncover the answer with dramatic prosperity. Ross Nickerson points out that several genre authors who experimented with genre rules set by the UN agency Poe were

girls, inventing a small genre of local detective fiction that flourished under their own name for many generations. Metta Fuller Victor's two detective novels, *The Dead Letter* (1867) and *The Eighth Picture* (1869). "Dead Letter" is noteworthy because it is the first full-length crime fiction work.

The period between the First and Second World Wars (20-1930s) is commonly referred to as the golden age of detective fiction. During this period a collection of very famous writers, as well as mostly English, but in addition well-known writers emerged. Female writers legitimize a significant portion of the well-known writers of the Golden Age. Agatha Christie, Dorothy L. Sayers, Josephine Tay, Margery Allingham, and other writers were some of the most famous women writers of our time. With the exception of the writer, they were all British. Various conventions of the detective genre were standardized throughout the Golden Age, and in 1929 a number of them were written by Ronald John Knox, the country's Catholic priest and author of detective stories, in his "Decalogue" in the rules of detective fiction. one of its rules was to avoid supernatural ingredients, so the main goal remained a mystery.

John Knox argues that the mystery "should consist of the disclosure of the mystery of the main interest; Another common convention in Golden Age detective stories belongs to the nursing association - usually a paid investigator or peacekeeper, but usually an early amateur - investigating a murder committed by one of a limited number of suspects. Throughout this sub-genre, the most common sub-genre of the novel has become a mystery story, with fine ingenuity also used in the narration of a crime, usually a murder, and consequently an investigation. The aim was to hide the identity of the perpetrator from the reader to the top of the book. According to students Carol Kismarik and Marvin Heiferman, "The golden age of detective fiction began with the smell of rose gardens, lowlands, and murderers hiding in beautiful villages.

During this period, several conventions of the detective-fiction genre developed, as different writers - from lawyers to well-known poets - tried themselves in mysterious stories. John Dixon, in addition, wrote as Carter Dixon - he used the "puzzle" method in his writing, which was unique to the reader. He is a master of the "locked cosmic mystery", creating clever and seemingly impossible plots. The two most popular work area units of machines are "Permanent Suicide Cases" (1941) and therefore *Hollow Man* (1935). Another author, Cecil Street - who also wrote as John Rod - wrote about Dr. Priestley, a detective who specializes in technical devices. Within the subgenre of the mystery story, it has been adopted and expanded by Rex Stout and Ellery Queen along with others. Throughout the Golden Age, the emphasis on formal rules was of a very standardized type, but created good works. The most popular novels of our time are "original and exciting plot; the difference within the writing, the sense of bright space, the unforgettable and captivating protagonist and therefore the ability to engage the reader in their own relaxing and ultra-individual world.

Agatha Christie was not only the most famous author of the Golden Age, but she was one of the most famous authors of all genres of all time, albeit a collective thinker. When he died in 1976, "he was a famous author in history. Most of the standard books of the Golden Age were written by Christie. He created a long series of books that included detective heroes such as *Hercules Poirot* and *Miss Marple*. His success is due to the fact that he bases his stories on complex puzzles "combined with his unimaginable heroes and beautiful bourgeois conditions".

In short, by writing this article, I gained a lot of knowledge about the detective genre and the masterpieces written in this genre. In the course of my research, I learned how and where the detective genre originated, when it peaked, and who contributed to its development.

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